

non-Faradaic electrolysis are described below :

(1) Increase of temperature increases the extent of co-liberation i. e., the cathode gas contains a larger per cent of oxygen and the anode gas contains a larger per cent of hydrogen. In other words, there is more oxygen at the cathode and very much more hydrogen at the anode under otherwise similar conditions.

(2) But the most striking feature is the fact that co-liberation even at the anode (and the other non-Faradaic features more or less) persists up to a very high current density, and to some extent at a much higher concentration. For example, at room temperature the gases cease to be explosive at about 10mA/cm², whereas at 60° the gases are explosive (even) at 50mA/cm² or even higher in suitable systems. This is shown in Table 1.

idea of charged water molecules carrying the current. The observed effect of temperature naturally helps increased formation of (H₂O)⁺ and (H₂O)⁻ near the anode and cathode respectively. Secondly, increase of temperature increases their mobility to the corresponding opposite electrode and thus help co-liberation.

References

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TABLE 1

K ₂ SO ₄ 40°C				K ₂ SO ₄ 60°C				K ₂ SO ₄ 80°C			
Strength	% O ₂ at		% H ₂ at	Strength	% O ₂ at		% H ₂ at	Strength	% O ₂ at		% H ₂ at
	i/mA	Cathode	Anode		i/mA	Cathode	Anode		i/mA	Cathode	Anode
0.001(N)	22	10.4**	23.3**	0.001(N)	1	31.4**	56.0**	0.001(N)	25	16.7**	29.0**
	22	13.6**	23.6**		1	32.1**	57.8**		26	17.7**	26.6**
	25	13.5**	21.6**		5	30.6**	45.9**				
	25	14.4**	22.5**		10	26.8**	38.9**				
			25		17.4**	20.5**					
0.01(N)				0.01(N)	5	33.7**	45.6**	0.01(N)			
					5	32.0**	50.2**				
					10	24.8**	38.5**				
	36.5	5.0*	6.1*				35		15.2**	25.0**	
	36	6.0*	6.9*	40	11.4**	19.2**	39		14.8**	28.0**	
40	0.6	4.8*	45	10.4**	18.9**	40	15.6**	27.3**			
40	1.4	3.7*	60	13.4**	22.8**	41	16.0**	25.9**			
						60	12.3**	23.1**			
						60	12.3**	23.0**			
0.1(N)	39	1.2	0.6	0.1(N)	40	1.2	1.3	0.1(N)	40	16.9**	23.7**
	39	1.0	0		41	1.1	1.3		40	16.4**	23.5**
	40	0.6	0		45	0.2	0.8		60	12.1**	15.7**
	40	0.3	0		45	0.2	0.5		60	12.9**	17.2**
							80		9.0**	6.0*	
							80		9.8**	1.6	

N.B. : ** means strongly explosive ; * means mildly explosive ; others do not explode on sparking.

Thus the limitations of low current density and low concentration which we have so far found to be essential for production of non-Faradaic features are mostly removed by an increase of temperature. Keeping concentration low (~N/1000), it is possible to increase the current density to as high as 25mA/cm² or even higher and still get explosive gases at both the electrodes or at least at the cathode. This is illustrated in Table 1. Also the concentration zone over which co-liberation takes place gets very much extended at higher temperature so much so that N/100 or even N/10 concentrations can be used to yield explosive cathode and anode gases provided the temperature is suitably high. Thus the present work has very much extended the frontier of activity for study of non-Faradaic electrolysis.

Various theories have been suggested to explain the anomalous features of non-Faradaic electrolysis. We have critically examined all of them in a separate paper⁴ and favour the one involving the

Quantitation of Copper in Some of the Copper Base Alloys by Paper Chromatographic Technique

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In an earlier communication¹ a method of direct assessment suitable for determining uranyl ion by photodensitometer after its paper chromatographic separation was proposed. The procedure described for evaluating unknowns quantitatively from strips run simultaneously for knowns and unknowns proved better than other known methods of direct spot evaluation in paper chromatography. To apply this technique for metal ion estimations in alloys, attempts have been made in this communication to separate and estimate copper in some of the

copper base alloys. The alloys in which copper has been estimated include—silver coin (Cu, 40%; Zn, 5%; Ag, 50%; Ni, 5%), monel alloy (Cu, 30.32%; Ni, 66.9%; Mn, 0.98%; Fe, 1.8%), cupronickel (Cu, 68.75%; Ni, 30.03%; Mn, 0.86%; rest Si, Fe, etc.), leaded brass (Cu, 59.2%; Pb, 2.0%; Fe, 0.045% and rest Zn), and aluminium bronze (Al, 10.8%; Mn, 0.30%; Fe, 5.58%; Cu, 83.32%, Sn and Pb, nil).

Experimental :

Preparation of alloy solutions :

A weighed quantity of the alloy (thoroughly cleaned) was taken in a small beaker (50 ml.), covered with distilled water and dissolved in nitric acid to get a clear solution by intermittent heating (if required). The excess of nitric acid was removed by careful evaporation of the solution to dryness and then the residue was extracted with distilled water. It was transferred into a 25 ml. normal flask and diluted up to the mark. Generally one gram (exactly) of the alloy was used for dissolution in 25 ml. of the solution, except in the cases of silver coin and monel alloy where the quantities taken were 1.1738 and 1.3088 gm. respectively.

Solvent System :

The solvent system used for developing and separating copper from other metal constituents of the alloys consisted of a combination of chloroform-methyl alcohol-amyl alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (46 : 23 : 23 : 8 v/v). It was chosen after several preliminary studies to get spots suitable for quantitation. The R_f values of different constituent metals of the alloys investigated with this solvent system were found out experimentally as below : Cu, 0.28 ; Ni, 0.14 ; Ag, 0.0 ; Zn, 0.65 ; Pb, 0.0 ; Mn, 0.09 ; Al, 0.08 and Fe(III), 0.56.

Procedure : The ascending technique was used with developing chambers consisting of glass jars (height, 30 cm. ; diameter, 10 cm.) provided with well greased glass lids for making them airtight and fitted with movable glass hangers. Paper strips of Whatman No. 1 (23 × 9 cm.) were used for this work. A chromatographic technique for development of knowns and unknowns was adopted as detailed in the previous communication (loc.cit.). A time interval of ~2 hours was allowed for development after which the strips were taken out, dried quickly and exposed to ammonia vapours for neutralizing the acid content of the paper. These were then subjected to a spray of a 0.3% w/v solution of rubeanic acid in ethanol which formed olive green derivative with the developed spots of copper ($R_f=0.28$). The colour deepened on thorough exposure of the spots to ammonia vapours. After drying, the paper strips were cut horizontally in a way suitable to get all the developed spots of the ion to be estimated. Such strips were fed to the photodensitometer (Type 201 Systronix, India) and each spot was scanned carefully and repeatedly.

The concentration of unknown (i.e., copper in the alloy sample) was estimated from calibration

curves of peak heights and concentration for knowns run simultaneously with the unknown (details as per Bhatnagar et al¹).

Using this technique quantitation of copper in the alloys listed above was carried out (see Table 1 for results).

Results and Discussion :

Though certain metal ions in alloys have been estimated by paper chromatography, yet none of these procedures is based on scanning technique as has been adopted and recommended in the present work. Thus polarography has been used to estimate cadmium in copper alloy² and zinc in soldering alloy³. Similarly colorimetry was used to estimate nickel, cobalt and copper in steel and minerals⁴.

The results of the present investigations have been compared with theoretical values of copper concentrations in the alloys investigated (Table 1)

TABLE 1

Alloy	Value for Cu(II) ion in $\mu\text{g}/\text{drop}$		Error %
	Theoretical	Experimental	
Silver coin	18.75	19.50	+4.0
Cupronickel	27.50	26.00	-5.4
Monel alloy	15.10	14.50	-3.9
Leaded brass	23.70	22.50	-5.0
Aluminium bronze	33.33	32.00	-3.9

and these can be compared with any of the known instrumental methods very well. Moreover, the method adopted was quick as far as scanning or estimation step was concerned. Very small quantities (10-50 μg per drop) of the material was needed in these estimations without loss of reasonable accuracy. Thus it can be said that the suggested procedure and the chloroformic solvent used here can be adopted for routine analysis of copper in such alloys conveniently.

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